

FLY on Cray: Porting, Optimization and Performance Analysis of Cosmological Simulation Code FLY on Cray XE6 Architecture

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Abstract

In this whitepaper we report work that was done to investigate and improve the performance of a mixed MPI and OpenMP implementation of the FLY code for cosmological simulations on a PRACE Tier-0 system Hermit (Cray XE6).

1. Introduction

FLY is a N-body code for cosmological simulations of the evolution of the Large Scale structure of the Universe [1]. The capability to simulate problems with a very large number of particles N (i.e. with a high mass resolution) is a particular focus of FLY. A three phase Barnes-Hut algorithm [2] is deployed to reduce the problem complexity. Prior to the start of the project, the code has been parallelised in MPI, allowing access to the large amount of memory available on distributed memory architectures. FLY scales as $N \log(N_p)$, with N denoting the number of bodies and N_p denoting the number of MPI tasks [1]. In order to improve the efficiency of the code, the latest version of FLY utilises threads via OpenMP to parallelise the MPI tasks within the nodes.

The aim of this work was to analyse the performance of the OpenMP parallelisation on the PRACE Tier-0 system Hermit at HLRS in Germany and advise the code authors on possible improvements to the application source. During our work we focused on two main tasks:

- Demonstrating that FLY is capable of simulating a very large number of bodies (up to several billions) on the Hermit system
- Examining the scalability of the new OpenMP part of the parallelisation, when an increasing number of threads is deployed within each node

The Hermit system utilizes Cray's XE6 architecture. It has 3552 compute nodes, each offering two 16 core AMD "Interlagos" processors with a nominal clock speed of 2.3 GHz. All performance measurements of FLY on Hermit were obtained with the use of 32GB nodes. The largest FLY jobs executed on the system used 32 nodes (512 AMD "Interlagos" cores) of Hermit. Methodology for performance analysis and optimization of the code was based on best practice guidelines for Cray XE6 architecture [3]. In Section 2 we briefly describe the porting process. In Section 3 we report and discuss the results of performance analysis of the FLY code on Hermit. Section 4 describes scalability results.

2. Porting to HERMIT system

Compilation and linking of FLY code on Hermit system was rather straightforward. We decided to compile the application with two different compilers available on Hermit system: GNU and Cray. The only difficulty that we encountered was that FLY holds significant data in static arrays. On Linux based operating systems this requires attention when compiling the code.

The default settings of the Cray and GNU compilers on Hermit do not allow for static data structures larger than 2GB, which are required by FLY when simulating a large number of bodies per MPI task. To enable large static data structures for the Cray

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compiler we had to generate position independent code by using the `-hpic` flag when compiling and for the linker the flag `-dynamic` was required in addition to prevent static linking. To enable large static arrays for the GNU compiler the flag `-mmodel=medium` was required when compiling and linking. Again at the linking step the flag `-dynamic` was necessary. To prepare for scalability testing we decided to compare OpenMP single node performance measured with both compilers. The results for 1,048,576 bodies are shown in Table 1.

	1 thread	2 threads	4 threads	8 threads	16 threads	32 threads
GNU	126 sec	83 sec	55 sec	45 sec	41 sec	46 sec
Cray	208 sec	144 sec	89 sec	60 sec	41 sec	33 sec

Table 1 Time taken for the entire code to compare the performance of the GNU and Cray compilers.

The single thread performance is much better for the GNU compiler. However the Cray compiler binaries achieve much better OpenMP scalability and the total execution time for 32 threads is significantly lower than the one measured with GNU binaries. Therefore the Cray compiler was chosen for the remainder of the project.

3. Performance analysis

In this section we describe the performance analysis steps that we have implemented. We start by describing the analysis of OpenMP implementation efficiency prepared with the use of the `craypat` tool. Next we show the results of code profiling of FLY.

3.1. Analysis of OpenMP implementation

Initial benchmarking of FLY showed that the scalability of the Barnes-Hut tree generation step was not satisfactory. To investigate this, the code was instrumented with the `craypat` performance analysis tool [4]. For this investigation we used 4,194,304 particles on a single node with a single MPI-task. Even for this problem size, which can be executed using static data structures smaller than 2GB, we observed performance issues similar to the ones encountered when using problem sizes requiring data structures of tens of giga bytes: The time spent for tree generation increased significantly when more than one thread was used. Moreover for a large number of threads tree generation would even not reach the performance level of utilising a single thread only.

The `craypat` report allowed us to trace the excessive time consumption to a single loop inside the tree generation routine, which on 1 thread consumed 1.6% of the total runtime, while on 4 threads this loop was responsible for 27% of the total time taken. Deeper inspection of the code showed that the loop contained two I/O statements. Removing these statements from the loop lead to a significant performance improvement for the loop in question, as shown in Table 2.

	1 thread	2 threads	4 threads	8 threads	16 threads
Original	7.7 sec	43 sec	31 sec	25 sec	24 sec
Optimised	2.8 sec	3.0 sec	3.0 sec	3.0 sec	2.8sec

Table 2 Time taken for the tree generation for different thread counts, before and after optimising the I/O statements in the tree generation routine.

The optimised tree generation leads to a significant improvement of the overall runtime, as shown in Table 3. Again these numbers are for 4,194,304 particles.

	1 thread	2 threads	4 threads	8 threads	16 threads
Original	308 sec	209 sec	120 sec	73 sec	50 sec
Optimised	304 sec	170 sec	90 sec	66 sec	34 sec

Table 3 Time taken for the entire code for different thread counts, before and after optimising the I/O statements in the tree generation routine.

3.2. Profiling

At the end of the project a final `craypat` profile using sampling was performed to ensure that code does not contain any unexpected performance bottlenecks. Again a problem size of 4,194,304 bodies was used for this study. The result is summarised in Figure 1. The most expensive routines `force` and `ilist` show very good scalability with the number of threads now. The routine `tree_gen` shows a speed-up when moving from 1 to 2 threads, but there is no further benefit from moving to higher thread counts. Due to the performance improvements this project made to the routine, its overall impact on the whole application’s scalability is minimal now. The proportion of time spent in library routines (marked as “ETC”) becomes more and more important when increasing the thread count. Further investigation would be required to understand whether the time in libraries could be reduced.

Figure 1 Profiling of the code at the end of the project. For different numbers of threads, the number of samples for the total code, the most expensive routines and library functions are shown.

4. Scalability tests

We have examined the OpenMP scalability of the FLY code. As described in [1] the application was designed and developed as a distributed code for grid environments and does not present either strong or weak scalability with increasing number of MPI processes. The strength of the FLY code lies in its ability to create large scale cosmological simulations with very big number of bodies. As it was described before one of the major objectives of the project was to examine the new mixed MPI and OpenMP version of the code. Measurements described here had two main purposes:

- show that FLY code is able to create simulations with a very large number of bodies (reaching few billions) on PRACE Tier-0 system,
- examine the scalability of the new OpenMP implementation of FLY with increasing number of threads used within each node.

Figure 2 Results of OpenMP scalability tests of the FLY code. Total execution time plotted against different number of threads for each run.

We have executed the following OpenMP scalability runs on the Hermit system:

- **1st run:** 2²⁶ bodies on single node for 1,2,4,8,16 and 32 OpenMP threads,
- **2nd run:** 2²⁷ bodies on 2 nodes for 1,2,4,8,16 and 32 OpenMP threads,
- **3rd run:** 2²⁸ bodies on 4 nodes for 1,2,4,8,16 and 32 OpenMP threads,
- **4th run:** 2²⁹ bodies on 8 nodes for 1,2,4,8,16 and 32 OpenMP threads,
- **5th run:** 2³⁰ bodies on 16 nodes for 1,2,4,8,16 and 32 OpenMP threads,
- **6th run:** 2³¹ bodies on 16 nodes for 1,2,4,8,16 and 32 OpenMP threads

Results of this case study are presented in Figure 2.

The final OpenMP scalability test was executed with 4,000,000,000 bodies on 32 nodes. The size of the job was carefully chosen in a way that the memory of each node was almost fully consumed (**in approx. 93%**). Total wall clock time obtained for different number of threads per node is presented in Table 4.

	2 threads	4 threads	8 threads	16 threads	32 threads
4 billion run	10764 sec	5969 sec	3451 sec	1848 sec	1053 sec

Table 4 Time taken for the entire code for different thread counts, 4 billion bodies run on 32 nodes.

Results presented above for the 4 billion body run should not be compared in terms of total time with previous scalability runs (those presented in Figure 2). The parameters of this specific run were changed since there was a threat of reaching the node hour limit assigned to our project on the Hermit system. The obtained results demonstrate that the FLY code is capable of simulating very large cosmological structures, reaching sizes competitive with the largest cosmological simulations ever. Moreover we have proved that OpenMP scalability improves with increasing bodies per core ratio. Using 32 threads for 4 billion bodies the code still displays a high efficiency level of 64% when comparing to utilising only 2 threads.

Improving the FLY performance further, would require heavy code modifications, going beyond the timeline of this project. Within the project group, we have discussed potential algorithmic and implementation optimizations that are necessary to reach a more satisfactory MPI scalability.

Conclusions

We have ported FLY successfully to Hermit. We have also identified mixed MPI and OpenMP implementation performance bottlenecks, investigated scalability and optimized its performance. Finally we have executed a large scale simulation to ensure that the FLY code is capable of simulating very large cosmological structures.

Within this work we were mainly focused on the OpenMP scalability since the performance of the MPI parallelization is already investigated by the code authors [1]. Further improvements to parallel performance of FLY would require heavy code modifications. Implementing these would be far beyond the timeline of our project. However based on the analysis of the application we were able to point out the most important algorithmic and implementation optimizations that are necessary to reach satisfactory MPI scalability results.

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